

The Impact of Teacher Social Competence for the Result of Social Subject Grade VIII in SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the influence of teacher social competence on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects in class VIII SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. The variables in this research are teacher social competence as the independent variable and learning outcomes as the dependent variable. This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach, with a research population of all class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar and a research sample of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar consisting of 146 students selected using simple random sampling (formula Slovin). Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. The results of this research show that: there is a positive and significant influence of teacher social competence on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the t value is calculated Teacher social competence (2.551) > t table value (1.65550) which means this variable is significant. The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.043, which means that 4.30% of the teacher's social competence variable influences student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 95.70% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

INTRODUCTION

In the current development of the world of education, it is also showing very rapid development. Therefore, this Junior High School (SMP) is the foundation for instilling the spirit of the nation's children to receive education so that they become nobler people in living an increasingly advanced and developing life. Education is a process that aims to change a person's attitudes and behavior to gain human maturity through teaching and training. Education is also an important demand in the development life of children, where the aim is to guide and direct their potential so that in the future they can achieve the highest safety and happiness as individuals and members of society.

The goals of education can be achieved if someone guides and directs the child's potential. One profession that can create these goals is a teacher. Teaching is a noble profession, ideally Indonesian teachers always appear professionally with their main task being to educate, guide, train and develop curriculum or curriculum tools, as the principle "ing ngarso sung tulodho, ing madya mangun karso , *tut wuri handayani* " states. This means that a teacher at the front provides a role model or example, in the middle provides initiative and at the back provides encouragement or motivation.

Competence is the teacher's ability to adapt to work demands in the surrounding environment when carrying out his duties as a teacher and as an educator he must have social competence. Because, in relation to educators or learning resources, teachers always maintain good communication with students, parents, neighbors and friends in the profession. Teachers' social competence is related to children's learning outcomes. Because how can children absorb lesson material well if the teacher lacks the ability to communicate with students and their parents.

It can be seen from the student learning results obtained by class VIII students when taking the social studies subject exam that it is still low or that there are still many students who get scores below the Minimum Completeness Criteria (KKM), where the KKM set by the school for the social science subject is 72.

Meanwhile, the social studies teacher hopes that 95% of students will succeed in achieving a score above the KKM in the Mid-Semester Assessment (PTS) exam in the social sciences subject, but in reality, seen from the Mid-Semester Assessment table, many students fail the social studies subject exam, where students who pass In the social studies exam there were only 82 students or 37% and 141 students or 63% did not complete it . From the results of the Mid-Semester Assessment (PTS) for class VIII students, it shows that learning outcomes are still low. According to one of the teachers interviewed by the researcher, students are still less active and do not dare to ask the teacher if they do not understand the material/lessons conveyed by the teacher, are silent when answering questions from the teacher, and are not motivated to present and explain a problem by giving discussion of the problems presented.

In the above phenomenon, researchers are interested in examining in more depth the social competence of teachers through research with the title. "The Influence Of Teachers' Social Competence On Student Learning Outcomes In The Social Science Subject Of Class Viii Students At Smp Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar"

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Teacher Social Competence

Social competence, stated by Buchari Alma in the journal Anggun Rahmawati and Indah Nartani (2018:1), is the teacher's ability to communicate and interact effectively with the school environment and outside the school environment . Mulyasa

in the journal Hazami and Anik Herminingsih (2017:7) argue that social competence is the ability of teachers as part of society to communicate and interact effectively with other people including: students, teachers, parents/guardians of students and the community. Teacher social competence is the ability and skill of a teacher to communicate and interact effectively in the implementation of the learning process and the community so that it has a positive impact on student learning outcomes for report cards.

2. Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes are defined as the level of success of students in studying subjects at school which is expressed in scores obtained from test results regarding a number of certain subject matters. Sudjana in Dani Firmansyah's journal (2015:4), learning outcomes are the abilities that students have after experiencing the learning process. According to Oemar Hamalik (2008: 155), learning outcomes are changes in behavior in a person that can be observed and measured in the form of knowledge, attitudes and skills. This change can be interpreted as an improvement and better development before those who did not know became those who knew. Learning outcomes have an important meaning in the teaching and learning process at school, which is a benchmark for success in the teaching and learning process. A person's mastery of learning outcomes can be seen from his behavior, namely behavior in the form of mastery of knowledge and thinking skills.

METHODS

The type of research carried out is descriptive quantitative research. This research is descriptive research because it aims to describe the facts and characteristics of a particular population or area in a systematic, factual and thorough manner. According to Sugiyono (2017:11) that "Quantitative Research can be interpreted as a research method that is based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, collecting data using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis, with the aim of testing the hypothesis has been implemented.

Based on the researcher's title " Influence Teachers' Social Competence on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Sciences (Social Sciences) Class VIII Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar ". So the research location and time of the research was carried out at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This research was carried out at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar in May 2023 to September 2023. The population in this study were all class VIII students at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar, totaling 233 students. The sample in this study was determined using the Slovin formula and obtained results in class VIII-1 totaling 21 students, class VIII-2 totaling 21 students, class VIII-3 totaling 21 students, class VIII-4 totaling 21 students, class VIII-5 totaling 21 students, class VIII-6 with 20 students and class VIII-7 with 21 students. From the results of the sample calculations carried out, it can be determined that the number of samples used was 146 students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The validity test in this study used SPSS version 25. The level used to test the validity of the instrument was 0.05 %. Based on the results of the validity test, 35 students were tested with a total of 25 questions.

The statement item is declared valid if the value of $r_{count} \geq r_{table}$ with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. From the results of the validity test, it can be seen that the correlation between each question item and the total score of $n = 35$ shows that the r table is 0.334. This means that if the correlation value is more than 0.334 then the question is considered valid.

Table 1 Results of Teacher Social Competency Validity Test

STATEMENT	r-count	r-table	Decision
1	0.627	0.334	VALID
2	0.733	0.334	VALID
3	0.419	0.334	VALID
4	0.555	0.334	VALID
5	0.627	0.334	VALID
6	0.386	0.334	VALID
7	0,627	0,334	VALID
8	0,555	0,334	VALID
9	0,386	0,334	VALID
10	0,733	0,334	VALID
11	0,555	0,334	VALID
12	0,733	0,334	VALID
13	0,386	0,334	VALID
14	0,733	0,334	VALID
15	0,627	0,334	VALID
16	0,733	0,334	VALID
17	0,374	0,334	VALID
18	0,733	0,334	VALID
19	0,399	0,334	VALID
20	0,419	0,334	VALID
21	0,555	0,334	VALID
22	0,627	0,334	VALID
23	0,386	0,334	VALID
24	0,733	0,334	VALID
25	0,386	0,334	VALID

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the data obtained is all > 0.334 , so it can be said that all statements are valid.

Instrument Reliability Test

For the questionnaire reliability criteria, if $r_{count} > r_{table}$ with a significant level ($\alpha = 0.05$) then the questionnaire is said to be reliable. However, if $r_{count} \leq r_{table}$ then the questionnaire is considered to have no reliability. If the *Cronbach Alpha value* is > 0.60 it is said to be reliable, but if the *Cronbach Alpha value* is < 0.60 it is said to be unreliable.

From the data obtained, it is known that the *Cronbach Alpha* obtained was $0.910 > 0.60$. From the results of calculating the reliability of teachers' social competence, it can be concluded that the research instruments used are reliable.

Data Normality Test

Figure 1. Normal Probability P-Plot Curve

Based on the test results of the p-plot graph, it shows the conclusion that the data is spread around the diagonal line, so the data is declared normal. This can be seen in figure 1 above.

Hypothesis testing Data Linearity Test

**Table 2 Linearity Test Results
 ANOVA ^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	477,826	1	477,826	6,509	,012 ^b
	Residual	10571,544	144	73,413		
	Total	11049,370	145			

a. Dependent Variable: STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES

b. Predictors: (Constant), TEACHER SOCIAL COMPETENCY

From the output table above, the significance value = 0.012 is obtained, which is smaller than 0.05 , because the significance is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that between the variables of teacher social competence and student learning outcomes there is a significant linear relationship.

Product Moment Correlation Test

Table 3 Results; Correlation of Teacher Social Competence with Student Learning Outcomes

		Correlations	
		STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE
<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES	1,000	,208
	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE	,208	1,000
Sig. (1- tailed)	STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES	.	,006
	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE	,006	.
N	STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES	146	146
	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE	146	146

From the results of the analysis above, it is known that 146 respondents produced a correlation value of 0.208. To interpret the strength of the relationship between two variables, this is done by looking at the correlation coefficient number calculated using the R value interpretation which is as follows.

- 0 : There is no correlation between two variables
- > 0 - 0.25 : Very weak correlation
- > 0.25 - 0.50 : Sufficient Correlation
- > 0.50- 0.75 : Strong Correlation
- > 0.75 - 0.99 : Very strong correlation
- 1 : Perfect Correlation

From the data above, it can be concluded that the teacher social competency variable (X) and the student learning outcome variable (Y) have a very weak relationship because they have a correlation value of 0.208.

Simple Linear Regression Equation Test

Table 4 Simple Linear Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	52,358	5,463		9,584	,000
	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE	,211	,083	,208	2,551	,012

In the table above, it is known that the constant value (a) is 52,358, indicating that if the teacher's social competence variable to improve learning outcomes is 0.211, that variable X to Y is said to be positive. So the regression equation is written:

$$Y = a + bX$$

$$Y = 52.358 + 0.211X$$

The equation can be translated:

1. A constant of 52.358 means that the consistent value of the participation variable is 52.358.
2. The regression coefficient

Using this equation, you can predict Y based on a given X. For example, If X is 54, then the prediction of Y will be $Y = 52.358 + 0.211(54)$

Coefficient of Determination Test

Table 5 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Model Summary ^b		
			Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,208 ^a	,043	,037	8,568	1,605

a. Predictors: (Constant), TEACHER SOCIAL COMPETENCY

b. Dependent Variable: STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES

1. The value of $R = 0.208$ or 20.8% means that there is a relationship between the variable (X) in the form of Teacher Social Competence on student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar in 2023.
2. The value R_{Square} is 0.043 or 4.30%, meaning the research variable is Teacher Social Competence able to influence student learning outcomes by 4.30% while the remaining 95.70% is influenced by other variables not discussed in this research such as learning motivation, learning discipline, learning facilities, learning environment and so on.

t test

Table 6 t test results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	52,358	5,463		9,584	,000
	TEACHER'S SOCIAL COMPETENCE	,211	,083	,208	2,551	,012

Based on the table above, the values show these criteria, so the values from *calculated t* and *t_{table}* will be needed. For the *calculated t*, it is obtained from the *t* value in the *Coefficient table*, while for the *T_{table}* it is obtained from the *t* table with a *t* table value of 1.65550, so it can be concluded that the value *t_{hitung}* of the teacher social competence variable is 2.551 and the value *t_{tabel}* is 1.655, so the value is $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$ ($2.551 > 1.655$) with a significance level of $0.012 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the teacher social competency variable partially has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects in junior high schools. Negeri 7 Pematangsiantar.

Discussion

Based on the statistical analysis that has been carried out on each research variable, the researcher tries to provide a discussion of the problems discussed in this research, namely: **The Influence of Teacher Social Competence (X) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) in Social Sciences Subjects in Middle Schools Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar in 2023**.

The test results show that partially the Teacher's Social Competence (X) has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes as variable (Y). This can be seen from the regression coefficient value of Teacher Social Competence (X) is 2.551 with a significance value of 0.012, so H_1 is accepted so that it can be concluded that Teacher Social Competence has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes in class VII social studies at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar in 2023.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Mukarramah Gustan. The Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Social Studies Learning Outcomes for Class VIII Students at SMP Negeri 6 Parepare. There is a significant influence between the teacher's social competence on the social studies learning outcomes of class VIII students at SMP Negeri 6 Parepare. In the output results above, a significant value = $0.025 < 0.05$ is obtained. So it can be concluded that a teacher must have social competence in understanding good teaching techniques in order to have an influence in improving student learning outcomes.

A teacher who has good teaching skills can certainly help improve students' understanding of the subject matter being presented, so that students can understand it easily, which will certainly have an impact on obtaining good test scores.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on research on the Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Student Learning Outcomes in Class VIII Social Sciences Subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar TA. 2023/2024, the conclusion obtained is that there is a positive and significant influence between Teacher Social Competence on the Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students in Social Sciences subjects at SMP Negeri 7 Pematang Siantar. This can be seen from the results of partial calculations (*t* test) on Teacher Social Competency (X) carried out using SPSS version 25, which shows the *calculated t* value $> t_{table}$ ($2.551 > 1.655$) and a significant value ($0.012 < 0.05$).

FURTHER STUDY

Due to the limitations in this research, it is hoped that future research will be more in-depth in exploring information and preparing instruments. So that more facts can be revealed that underlie teachers' social competence on student learning outcomes.

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REFERENCES

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2006. *Research Procedures: A Practice Approach* . Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Calhoun. 1995. *Psychology Of Adjustment And Human Relationships (New York, Mc Graw-Hill , Inc)* p, 90
- Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with the IBM SPSS 25 Program*. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency: Semarang.
- Hamalik, Oemar. 2008. *Teaching Planning Based on Approach* . System. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
- Istarani & Intan Pulungan. 2015 . *Encyclopedia of Education* . Medan: Media Persada.
- Kunandar. 2007. *Professional Teachers, Implementation of the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP) and preparation for Teacher Certification* , Jakarta :: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- Mulyasa, E. 2007. *Competency Standards and Teacher Certification* , Bandung: Teen Rosda Karya, Alfabeta.
- Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards
- Purwanto, Ngalm. 2007. *Educational Psychology* . Bandung: PT Teen. Rosdakarya.
- Riduwan. 2011. *Easy Learning to Research for Teacher-Employees and Beginner Researchers* . Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sardiman. 2012. *Teaching and Learning Interaction and Motivation* . Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada
- Siregar, Nurliani. 2015. *Education Profession* . Pematangsiantar: HKBP Nommensen University. 2018. *Introduction to Education* . Pematangsiantar: HKBP Nommensen University.
- Siyoto, Sandu. & Ali Sodik. 2015. *Basic Research Methodology* . Yogyakarta. Media Literacy.
- Sudjana, Nana. (2011). *Basics of the Teaching and Learning Process* . Bandung: Sinar Baru Algesindo.
- Sugiyono. 2011. *Educational Research Methods* . Bandung: Alfabeta. 2013. *Quantitative, Qualitative and R&D Research Methods*. Bandung: Alfabeta. 2014. *Educational Research Methods, Quantitative Qualitative Approach, and R&D* . Bandung: PT Alfabet. 2017. *Educational Research Methods, Quantitative Qualitative Approach, and R&D* . Bandung: PT Alfabet. 2018. *Quantitative, Qualitative, and R&D Research*

Methods. Bandung: Alfabeta. 2019. *Quantitative Research Methods*. Bandung. Alfabeta. 2022. *Quantitative Research Methods*. Yogyakarta: Alfabeta

Sujarweni. 2020. *Research Methodology*. Yogyakarta: New Library.

Suyanto. 2013. *Becoming a Professional Teacher (Strategy to Improve Teacher Qualifications and Quality in the Global Era)*, Erlangga Group, Jakarta.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers. Bandung: Citra Umbara

Uno, Hamzah, B. 2007. *Learning models create creative and effective teaching and learning processes*. Rawamangun: PT Bumi Aksara.

Ahmad, Mohammad Aswar. 2019. Communication as a Form of Teacher Social Competence in Schools. *Commodification Journal*. Vol.3, No. <https://journal3.uin-alauddin.ac.id/index.php/Komodifikasi/article/view/9968>

Fauhah, Homroul. 2021. Analysis of the *Make A Match* Learning Model on Student Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Office Administration Education*, Vol.9, No.2. <https://journal.unesa.ac.id/index.php/jpap/article/view/10080>

Firmansyah, Dani. 2015. The Influence of Learning Strategies and Learning Interest on Mathematics Learning Outcomes. *Unsika Education Journal*, Vol.3, No.1. <https://journal.unsika.ac.id/index.php/judika/article/view/199>

Hazami, & Anik Herminingsih. 2017. The Influence of Teacher Competence on Learning Effectiveness. *Scientific Journal of Management and Business*, Vol.3, No.3. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/462211/Influence-kompetensi-guru-terhadap-bisnis-pembelajaran>

Nurhayati. 2014. Improving Student Learning Outcomes Using the Science Subject Guidance Method in Class III of SD Inpres 1 Binaa. *Tadulako Online Creative Journal*, Vol.4, No. 10. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/119039>

Rahmawati, Anggun, & Indah Nartani. 2018. Social Competence of Teachers in Communicating Indonesian Language Learning at State Elementary School Rejowinan gun 3 Kotagede Yogyakarta. *Journal of Elementary Education*, Vol. 4, No. 3. <https://jurnal.ustjogja.ac.id/index.php/trihayu/article/view/2600>

Sinaga, Christian. 2022. The Relationship between E-Learning During the Covid-19 Pandemic and Learning Outcomes of Civics Study Program Students, Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, Darma Agung University Medan. *Journal of Pancasila and Citizenship Education*, Vol.4, No.1. [file:///C:/Users/Person1/Downloads/1546-217-3613-1-10-20220609%20\(3\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Person1/Downloads/1546-217-3613-1-10-20220609%20(3).pdf)

- Solikah, Sofiyah, Maratus, et al. 2023. The Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Muhammadiyah Learning Achievement at SMA Muhammadiyah 1 Surakarta. *Journal on Education* , 6 (1), 2530–2539. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v6i1.3277>
- Monisa, Nova, et al. 2021. *Educational Psychology and Professional Education*. The thesis is not published. Banda Aceh: Ar-Raniry Islamic State University. <https://www.studocu.com/id/document/universitas-islam-negeri-ar-raniry/sociology/psikologi-pendidikan-dan-pendidikan-profesional/46542717>
- Yani, Handra. 2013 . *The Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Student Learning Outcomes*. The thesis is not published. Pekanbaru: FTI Kasim Riau State Islamic University. [file:///C:/Users/Personal/Downloads/null% 20\(3\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Personal/Downloads/null%20(3).pdf)
- Gustan, Mukarramah. 2021. *The Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Social Studies Learning Outcomes* . The thesis is not published. Parepare: Tarbiyah Faculty, State Islamic Institute. <http://repository.iainpare.ac.id/id/eprint/3423>
- Sanlain, Fridolina. 2023. *The Influence of Teacher Social Competence on Student Learning Outcomes in Economics Subjects*. The thesis is not published. Kupang: FKIP Nusa Cendana University. [http://skrip.undana.ac.id/Ind ex.php ?p =show_detail&id=13190](http://skrip.undana.ac.id/Index.php?show_detail&id=13190)